

№2

2023 | АПРЕЛЬ

ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР АХБОРОТНОМАСИ

НАУЧНЫЙ ВЕСТНИК
SCIENTIFIC BULLETIN

ISSN: 2181-4554
DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-4554

ВЕСТНИК СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ-I, НОМЕР-2

**ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

I-ЖИЛД, 2-СОН

BULLETIN OF CONTEMPORARY STUDIES

VOLUME-I, ISSUE-2

ТОШКЕНТ – 2023

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Page Maker\Верстка\Саҳифаловчи: Абдураҳмон Хасанов

Таҳририят манзили: <https://imfaktor.uz>, 100152, Тошкент шаҳри, Учтепа тумани, “Ватан” МФЙ, Чилонзор 24-мавзеси, 2/27-уй.

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ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР АХБОРОТНОМАСИ

ВЕСТНИК СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | BULLETIN OF CONTEMPORARY STUDIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7865896>

“AUXILIARY VERB THAT REALIZES THE SITUATION IN THE FORM OF ACTION - ABOUT ETMEK”

ANNOTATSIYA

Information is provided about the analysis of the auxiliary verb - etmek, which realizes the situation in the form of action.

Key words: etmek, lexeme, sema, main meaning, independent meaning, adverb, adjective, verb, modal word.

After Uzbekistan gained independence, the need to learn and teach foreign languages increased. After all, perfect mastery of foreign languages, in turn, makes it possible to train experts in this field, translators. This situation creates an opportunity to strengthen social, cultural and economic relations with foreign countries. Therefore, it is important to research and identify the specific features of foreign languages, including the Turkish language.

Phonetic, lexical, morphological, syntactic features of the Turkish language have been specially studied in a number of studies by Turkish and foreign linguists, including Russian Turkologists. There are several monographs and scientific works created and published in this direction.

In particular, the issues of lexicology of the Turkish language have been the object of some special studies. Below we will consider the semantic analysis of the Turkish verb etmek.

The verb etmek is one of the active auxiliary verbs in the Turkish language. This auxiliary verb comes together with words belonging to the noun family in a broad sense and forms compound verbs.

Masalan: *Sen, Sara Hanımla yemeğe devam edersin (R.N.G.). You continue to eat with Mrs. Sarah.*

The verb etmek can be used alone. In this case, the meaning of the word is understood in the context, however, this verb lexeme has the same meaning as the words “yapmak” and “kılmak”. For example: **Eden** bulur, *ünleyen ölür (Atasözü).*

He who seeks finds. The verb etmek in this proverb actually means “to do”, “to work”, “to engage”.

In the context of the auxiliary verb etmek, it is possible to express the meaning of “doing something bad, behaving badly”: **Etme** komşuna gelir başına *(Atasözü).* *If you do harm to your neighbor, it will come back to you. Felek bana neler etti? (R.H.K.) Fate did not put days on my head?*

The auxiliary verb etmek can appear with the following word groups:

Noun + etmek auxiliary verb: *Mesela beraber dansettiğimizi farzedelim (R.N.G.). For example, let's imagine that we danced together.*

Adverb + etmek auxiliary verb: *Kolombo dönüşü ne varsa **altüst etmiş** (R.H.K.). His return to Colombo turned everything upside down.*

Modal word+ etmek auxiliary verb: *Seni kurtarmalı fakat **yok etmekle** de kurtarmak mümkündür (R.H.K.). You need to be saved, you can be saved only by destroying.*

Adjective + etmek auxiliary verb: *Onu yakından çehreme bakmaya **mecbur etmek** için adeta yüzünüzce uğraşıyordum (R.N.G.). I was almost frantically trying to get him to look at my face.*

The auxiliary verb *etmek* in the presence of nouns expresses the meaning of the realization of the concept understood from the main component: *Sana bir aydır yazmadım diye **şikayet ediyorsun** (H.E.A.). You complain that I haven't written to you in a month. In this example, the lexeme **etmek** was additionally used to turn the abstract concept of the word “**complaint**” into an action, that is, to express the negative attitude of the performer of the action to any work or situation that was not acceptable to him.*

The verb **etmek** can express the meaning of “to be engaged in a certain temporary work, to be engaged in”. For example: *Bir gün raslantılar gene bizi karşılaştırır, yatışmış olabiliriz; korkuzca **arkadaşlık ederiz!** One day he will meet us again, then we can calm down and become friends without fear. In this example, the verb to act with the word “**friendship**” expresses the meaning of the speaker's non-permanent, but, on the contrary, action and situation that occurred over a certain period of time.*

The verb **etmek**, similar to “to do some action, to engage in work”, can realize the following nuances of meaning directly depending on the meaning of the word it is combined with:

Based on the scope of meaning of the leading component, the verb to act carries the meaning of physical action, doing work: *Ben **telefon edeyim**, bavulların gönderilip gönderilmediğini sorayım, akşama **hareket edeceğini** de haber vereyim (R.H.K.). I will call and ask whether your bags have been sent or not, and inform you that I will be leaving in the evening. The verbs *telefon etmek* and *hareket etmek* in these sentences express the content of doing something physically.*

The verb *etmek* expresses mental work, mental work based on the direct text, as well as the syntactic framework. For example: *Bunları vapur yolcularından bir ispanyol bilgini bana okuduğu kendi dilinde bir kitaptan **tercüme ederek** söylüyor (R.H.K.).*

The verb *etmek* expresses mental work, mental work based on the direct text, as well as the syntactic framework. For example: *Bunları vapur yolcularından bir ispanyol bilgini bana okuduğu kendi dilinde bir kitaptan **tercüme ederek** söylüyor (R.H.K.). A Spanish scientist who is one of the passengers of the steamboat is speaking from a book in his native language. *Demek ki Kabil`den donusumu **hesap etmiş**, beni çağırıyor (R.H.K.). So he has calculated that I will return from Kabul and is calling me. The lexemes *tercüme-etmek-* to translate, *hesap etmek-* to calculate in this sentence mean the actions performed by the mind and knowledge of the person performing the action.**

The auxiliary verb *etmek* is written separately when it comes with words of two or more syllables. When this verb comes with one-syllable nouns, it is added.

Compare: *Yalnız **dikkat et**. Ateşin şiddeti sana mantığındaki selameti **kaybettirmesin** (R.N.G.). Just pay attention. Do not let the intensity of the fire lose your logical observation. When the auxiliary verb **etmek** comes with some monosyllabic words, the consonant at the end of the word is doubled. For example: *Sıcağı duymuyordum ve aklımdan geçerdiklerim için nezaketten olsun özür dilemeğe gerek **hissetmiyordum** (R.H.K.). I didn't feel the heat and I felt the need to apologize for what I had experienced. When the verb *etmek* is used with some words, the vowel in the last syllable is omitted and this word is added to the auxiliary verb: **azim+etmek –azmetmek, bahis+etmek –bahsetmek, hüküm+etmek-hükmetmek, keşif+etmek-keşfetmek.****

As a result of the analysis of the examples, we can conclude the following: The verb **etmek** ranks second among auxiliary verbs in the Turkish language according to its activity. This verb lexeme can be used alone, but mostly it comes with nouns in a broad sense. It is necessary to recognize that the singular use of the verb to commit often depends on the context. It is observed that the verb **etmek** expresses more than twenty meanings depending on the syntactic environment, the context and the meaning of the subordinate component attached to it.

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Муассис: «IMFAKTOR Pages» масъулияти чекланган жамияти.

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